

Extraction-spectrophotometric Determination of Bismuth(III) in Soil and Ore using Iodide and Amidines

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Manuscript received 5 July 1990, revised 24 January 1991,
accepted 28 March 1991

THE classical iodide method for the determination of bismuth is critical since it is applicable only in sulphurous acid medium and possesses the interference of many metal ions¹. Many dyes² were recommended to enhance the sensitivity of the classical iodide method. Earlier, *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidines were used for extraction-spectrophotometric determination of Sb^{III}, Au^{III} and As^{III} as halogeno ternary complexes³. The present paper deals with the extraction of Bi^{III} as its iodo-complex in chloroform with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine and its 8 derivatives.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spekol spectrophotometer matched with quartz cells of 1 cm path length was used for absorbance measurements. The standard solution of bismuth(III) was prepared by dissolving bismuth sulphate in dilute sulphuric acid (0.5 *M*) and standardised volumetrically with EDTA using pyrocatechol violet as an indicator⁴. Freshly prepared solutions of KI (5%, w/v) containing ascorbic acid (1%, w/v) was used. A 0.4% (w/v) solution of amidines⁵ in chloroform was employed for all extraction purpose. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade (B.D.H./E. Merck).

Procedure: To the standard solution of Bi^{III} (upto 450 μg) was added KI solution (1 ml) followed by 10 *M* H₂SO₄ to adjust the acidity in a final 10 ml aqueous solution. The solution was shaken with chloroform solution (10 ml) of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(4-chlorophenyl)benzamidine (PCPBA). The total organic phase was made upto 25 ml and the absorbance was measured at 490 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The maximum absorbance of the binary complex in aqueous solution and that of the ternary complex in chloroform is exhibited at 440 and 490 nm, respectively. The reagent blank in chloroform shows some absorbance at the λ_{max} hence it was used as reference for all absorbance measurements.

Various polar and non-polar organic solvents were tried for extraction of the metal, and chloroform was found to be most suitable. H₂SO₄ and HCl were tested for extraction of the metal with iodide and amidines and the former was used for acidity adjustment. The optimum acidity for the maximum

and constant colour development of the complex was found to be 0.5–3.0 *M* H₂SO₄.

At least 0.0075 *M* KI is required for the complete extraction of the analyte and no adverse effect on the absorbance is observed upto 0.1 *M* in aqueous solution. Ascorbic acid is added to prevent the liberation of iodine via oxidation of iodide as well as to remove oxidants, if any, present in the aqueous solution. At least 0.009 *M* PCPBA is needed for complete extraction and full colour development of the complex and no adverse effect was seen upto 0.07 *M* PCPBA. The absorbance of the extracted Bi^{III}-I⁻-PCPBA complex in chloroform remains unaltered when the volume ratio of organic to aqueous phase is varied from 2:1 to 1:8. The extraction of the complex is not affected by variation of the temperature of aqueous solution in the range 10–30°.

The system obeyed Beer's law over the range 0–16.5 μg Bi per ml with PCPBA having a correlation coefficient value of 0.98. The extraction of Bi^{III} with 9 amidines in presence of iodide gives a molar absorptivity range of (0.56–1.38) $\times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Of the 9 amidines tested, *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(4-chlorophenyl)benzamidine (PCPBA) gave the most sensitive colour reaction ($\epsilon = 1.38 \times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and therefore it was selected for the detailed experiments. The detection limit of the method is 0.01 μg Bi per ml. The relative standard deviation of the method for 10 replicate determinations at a level of 150 μg Bi per 25 ml of chloroform is $\pm 1.1\%$.

The substitution of CH₃ or Cl groups in imino N-ring of amidine causes reverse effects, i.e. the colour intensity of the complex increases with the introduction of CH₃ group in the order, *o*- > *m*- > *p*-, while in the case of Cl_o group the intensity increases in the order, *p*- > *m*- > *o*-.

Curve-fitting method was applied for the stoichiometric analysis of the complex. The results indicate the formation of a 1:4:2, Bi^{III}: I⁻: PCPBA complex in chloroform. The overall reaction may be given as

where, subscripts o and HA denote to the organic phase and amidine, respectively.

The effect of diverse ions in the determination of 150 μg Bi^{III} was examined and the tolerance limits of various diverse ions (in mg) found are as follows: Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} (0.6 each); Ag^I (1.2); Sb^{III} (3.0); V^V, W^{VI} (3.5 each); Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Re^{VII} (5.5 each); La^{III}, Mo^{VI} (25 each); U^{VI} (55); Al^{III} (70); Cr^{III}, Tl^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV} (95 each); Mn^{II}, Be^{II} (125 each); Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} (200 each); bromide, fluoride, oxalate (50 each); chloride, phosphate, EDTA (75 each); thiourea (60). Cu^{II} was masked with thiourea (25 g).

The present method was applied for the recovery of the metal in soil and galena samples obtained from Sonakhan mines (Raipur) and Zawar mines (Udaipur) respectively. The results obtained by the present method were in good agreement to the results

of thiourea method (in paranthesis) : 37.8 (39.0) and 12.0 (13.5) ppm.

References

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